

Dublin Chemistry Third Year Postgraduate Talks 2026

Report by: Yurii K. Gun'ko *

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Venue: School of Chemistry, Trinity College Dublin

Event Type: Symposium

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Trinity College Dublin
Coláiste na Tríonóide, Baile Átha Cliath
The University of Dublin

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Event Sponsors

-Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section

-Eli Lilly

- School of Chemistry, University of Dublin, Trinity College.

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Summary

The Dublin Chemistry Third-Year PhD Talks 2026 took place on 27 May 2026 at the School of Chemistry, Trinity College Dublin. The event brought together over 100 third-year PhD students and academic staff from Trinity College Dublin, University College Dublin and Technological University Dublin. This annual event provides an excellent opportunity to present and discuss current chemistry research, share scientific knowledge and ideas, and develop professional networks across the 3 institutions. 41 students presented their research across twelve thematic sessions covering organic, medicinal, physical, polymer, macrocyclic and sustainable chemistry, as well as nanotechnology and asymmetric catalysis. Each presentation was followed by questions and evaluated by academic assessors. The event concluded with a reception and an awards ceremony recognising the best postgraduate student presentations.

Attendees

Over 100 third-year PhD students and academic staff from Trinity College Dublin, University College Dublin and Technological University Dublin.

Target audience: academics and postgraduates

Programme

Please see the full programme below (next page).

About the Third Year Talks

The Dublin Chemistry Third-Year Postgraduate Talks is an established annual event. The event was developed as a collaborative initiative to strengthen links between the three institutions and to provide research students with an opportunity to present their work to a broad scientific audience outside their immediate research groups. The principal purpose of the event is to support the professional development of postgraduate researchers. By preparing and delivering a formal scientific presentation, students gain valuable experience in explaining their research clearly, responding to questions and communicating with

Third Year PhD Talks Programme 2026
School of Chemistry, Trinity College Dublin, Wednesday May 27th 2026
(Chairs in green, Supervisor in Red), each talk is strictly 20 minutes, including questions

9.15-9.25: Chem LLT . Welcome: Professor Yurii Gun'ko			
Talks	Chem LLT Sessions A1 – A4	Chem Sci LT Sessions B2/B3	SS Room Sessions C1 – C4
9.30 - 10.30	A1: Organic Chemistry 1 C. Loh and A. Palma Gawain Boyce Gilheany Rónán Brennan Hooper/ Baumann A. Petronilli McGarrigle/ Baumann	B1: Nanotechnology 1 Y. Gun'ko & B. Creaven G. Almohammadi Johnson/Rice Eleanor Cripwell Dunne I. Martinez Chauvin Brougham	C1: Physical Chemistry Platnich & Achilleos Chloé Flandrin McAuley Niall Murphy Brougham/Buckin Rocco Villano Negahdar
Tea/Coffee (School of Chemistry, TCD)			
11.00 - 12.30	A2: Organic chemistry 2 C. Loh and A. Palma Aisling Byrne McGarrigle Diarmuid O'Hanlon Baumann Maximilian O'Neill McGarrigle Oana Popa McGarrigle	B2: Nanotechnology 2 Platnich & Achilleos B. Moura Motta Dawson Caroline O'Sullivan Gun'ko Hend Shayoub Quinn Camille Legentil Dawson& Yan	C2: Macrocyclic Chemistry E. McGarrigle & B. Creaven Freya Ritterling Senge Camilla DiGirolamo Palma Sophie Kavanagh Byrne
Lunch (Campus Outlets)			
2.00 - 3.30	A3: Medicinal Chemistry 1 D. Gilheany & D. Brougham Amélia Auville Quinn Matthew Rowe Scanlan Yunhai Li O'Reilly Soumashree Sengupta Senge	B3: Sustainable Chemistry 1 J. Sullivan & P. Colavita Orlagh Beggs McDonald Caoimhe Maher Achilleos Patrick Saunders Achilleos R. Rajesh Elghobashi-Meinhardt	C3: Asymmetric Catalysis E. McGarrigle & Y. Gun'ko Paul Nolan Guiry Eoghan Courtney Guiry Jordan Smyth Guiry Ava Rogers Guiry
Tea/Coffee (School of Chemistry, TCD)			
4.00 - 5.00	A4: Medicinal Chemistry 2 D. Gilheany & D. Brougham Smit Patel Elghobashi-Meinhardt Kacper Kluza Evans Thomas Rabbitte Byrne	B4: Sustainable Chemistry 2 J. Sullivan & P. Colavita A.Cañete Arché Watson/ Melchor Diana Bura Trujillo/ Connon C. O hUallachain Keene	C4: Polymer Chemistry Y. Gun'ko & R. Padamati Aoife Donohoe Delaney Julie Mason McGouran Jack Moore Morris

5.15: Reception, Pavilion Pub, TCD

5.30: Awarding of Prizes

5.45: Closing

scientists from different areas of chemistry. These presentation and communication skills are essential for future careers in academia, industry and other professional sectors. The talks also provide an opportunity for students to learn about the wide range of chemistry research being undertaken across Dublin. The programme covers multiple areas of chemical science and encourages interaction, discussion and potential collaboration between students and researchers from the participating institutions. Overall, the Dublin Chemistry Third-Year Postgraduate Talks promotes scientific communication, interdisciplinary engagement and a stronger chemistry postgraduate research community across Dublin's universities.

Prizes

Congratulations to the Best talk postgraduate prize winners: Oana Popa, Hend Shayoub, Niall Murphy and Kacper Kluzka from UCD and Diana Bura and Julie Mason from TCD (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Third Year Postgraduate Talks prize winners.

Acknowledgements

We gratefully acknowledge Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section, Eli Lilly and School of Chemistry, Trinity College for financial support.

Previous Events in the Series

The Third Year Talks Symposium has taken place every year since 2011 as part of the Dublin Chemistry programme. Some recent events have more detailed reports available:

2025 Third Year Talks: News item from UCD Chemistry <https://www.ucd.ie/chem/newsevents/newsarchive/dublinchemistry3rdyeartalks2025/>

2024 Third Year Talks: News item from UCD Chemistry <https://www.ucd.ie/chem/newsevents/newsarchive/3rdyeartalks2024/>